

Synthesis, spectral characterization and antimicrobial studies of Schiff base hetero binuclear complexes of Rb^I and Cs^I

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Manuscript received 08 February 2010, revised 27 October 2010, accepted 03 November 2010

Abstract : A series of Schiff base hetero binuclear complexes of rubidium(I) and caesium(I) of the type $[M_a(acac)_2en.M_bL]$, where $M_a = Cu$ or Ni , $M_b = Rb$ or Cs , $acac = acetyl\ acetone$, $en = ethylenediamine$, $L = deprotonated\ o\text{-nitrophenol}$, $2,4\text{-dinitrophenol}$, $2,4,6\text{-trinitrophenol}$, $1\text{-nitroso-2-naphthol}$ or $8\text{-hydroxyquinoline}$ have been prepared by the reaction of $[M_a(acac)_2en]$ with rubidium or caesium metal salts of corresponding organic acids in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The complexes have been characterized by various physico-chemical techniques such as elemental analysis, molar conductance measurements, magnetic susceptibility measurements, infrared spectra and UV-Visible spectra. The complexes have been screened for their antibacterial activity against bacteria *Escherichia coli* MTCC 739, *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC 96 and for antifungal activity against fungus *Candida albicans* MTCC 227.

Keywords : Hetero binuclear complexes, IR spectra, UV-Visible spectra, antimicrobial studies, MIC.

Introduction

The literature survey reveals that Schiff bases are important coordinating ligands and metal complexes derived from Schiff bases occupy an important position in coordination chemistry due to their reactivity and physico-chemical properties¹. Schiff bases act as an excellent ligand with nitrogen or oxygen as donor atom and their metal complexes find versatile applications as homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts^{2,3}. The Schiff bases possess anticancer, antibacterial properties and have been used as anticancer, antitubercular, antibacterial, antifungal and hypertensive reagents^{4,5}. The coordination complexes containing Schiff bases as ligand can be utilized to unfold the mechanism of various biological activities occurring in nature⁶.

In the present communication, efforts have been made to describe the synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activities of a series of Schiff base hetero binuclear complexes of the type $[M_a(acac)_2en.M_bL]$, where $M_a = Cu$ or Ni , $M_b = Rb$ or Cs , $acac = acetylacetone$, $en = ethylenediamine$, $L = deprotonated\ o\text{-nitrophenol}$, $2,4\text{-dinitrophenol}$, $2,4,6\text{-trinitrophenol}$, $1\text{-nitroso-2-naphthol}$ or $8\text{-hydroxyquinoline}$.

Results and discussion

The complexes obtained are listed in Table 1. All the

complexes are coloured solid and stable at room temperature. The complexes are generally soluble in methanol, acetone, DMF and DMSO but insoluble in water. Formulation of these complexes has been made on the basis of their elemental analytical data, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility values. Molar conductance values of all the complexes were measured in DMSO at 20 (± 0.5) °C and at a concentration of $10^{-3} M$. Low value ($0.6\text{--}4.6\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$) of molar conductivity of the complexes adequately confirm the non-electrolytic nature of the metal complexes⁷.

Infrared spectra :

For bis(acetylacetone)ethylenediamine, a broad absorption band is observed at 3150 cm^{-1} . This may be due to the stretching vibration of an O-H group which supports structure I or may correspond to N-H str. vibration which supports structure II⁸. Absence of IR band in the region $\sim 1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates absence of any C=O group. So, a cage structure involving six membered rings containing hydrogen bond has been suggested⁹. When the ligand underwent complexation with Cu^{II} or Ni^{II} , the band at 3150 cm^{-1} disappeared. So, structure III has been suggested for the metal chelate⁸ (Fig. 1). It is expected that coordination of nitrogen to the metal atom might reduce the electron density in the azomethine link and thus C=N str. frequency in the complexes was observed at ~ 1500

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the Schiff base hetero binuclear complexes

Compd.	Colour	Melt. (m)	Molar cond.	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Analysis (%) :					Yield (%)
		Dec. (d)/Trans. (t) temp. (°C)	($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1})		Found (Calcd.)					
					C	H	N	M _a	M _b	
Cu(acac) ₂ en.RbTNP	Yellow	200m	3.8	Dia.	35.85 (36.05)	3.30 (3.33)	11.70 (11.68)	10.48 (10.60)	13.98 (14.26)	70.12
Cu(acac) ₂ en.CsTNP	Yellow	220m	2.6	Dia.	31.98 (33.41)	2.92 (3.0)	10.68 (10.82)	9.75 (9.82)	20.28 (20.55)	75.21
Cu(acac) ₂ en.RbDNP	Orange	260d	0.8	Dia.	40.32 (38.98)	3.82 (3.79)	9.78 (10.10)	10.95 (11.46)	15.20 (15.42)	50.69
Cu(acac) ₂ en.CsDNP	Deep brown	190m	4.6	Dia.	36.38 (35.91)	3.45 (3.49)	8.98 (9.31)	10.15 (10.56)	21.90 (22.12)	54.18
Cu(acac) ₂ en.Rb8HQ	Pale green	270md	0.9	Dia.	48.65 (48.93)	4.58 (4.66)	7.98 (8.15)	11.95 (12.33)	16.20 (16.59)	40.35
Cu(acac) ₂ en.Cs8HQ	Pale green	280md	1.2	Dia.	45.20 (44.80)	4.28 (4.26)	7.38 (7.46)	10.88 (11.29)	22.95 (23.63)	35.41
Ni(acac) ₂ en.RbTNP	Yellow	162m	4.1	Dia.	36.65 (36.35)	3.38 (3.36)	11.70 (11.78)	9.78 (9.78)	14.18 (14.38)	60.70
Ni(acac) ₂ en.CsTNP	Light brown	190m	3.2	Dia.	31.98 (33.65)	3.02 (3.11)	10.82 (10.91)	8.30 (9.14)	19.98 (20.71)	71.50
Ni(acac) ₂ en.CsDNP	Yellowish green	220m	4.5	Dia.	34.88 (36.20)	3.48 (3.51)	9.12 (9.38)	9.58 (9.83)	21.85 (22.27)	44.44
Ni(acac) ₂ en.Rb1N2N	Brown	195m	0.9	Dia.	50.28 (49.05)	4.47 (4.45)	7.68 (7.80)	10.72 (10.90)	15.75 (15.88)	30.56
Ni(acac) ₂ en.Rb8HQ	Pale green	280md	0.6	Dia.	48.80 (49.39)	4.65 (4.70)	8.20 (8.23)	11.42 (11.50)	16.65 (16.75)	33.56

where m – sharp melting point, d – decomposition temperature and md – melting with decomposition.

cm^{-1} indicating coordination of the Schiff bases through azomethine nitrogen¹⁰ and band $\sim 1120 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to enolic C–O str.^{11,12} whereas band $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to C=C str. When the metal chelates Cu(acac)₂en and Ni(acac)₂en formed oxygen bridged adducts with rubidium or caesium metal salts of organic acids, there was lower shifting in the C–O str. band which indicates coordination of enolic oxygen with Rb or Cs metal. The bands in the far infrared region i.e. 408–494 cm^{-1} and 508–590 cm^{-1} in the binuclear complexes are assigned to M–N str. and M–O str. modes respectively¹³. These bands are not present in the ligand, bis(acetylacetonate)ethylenediamine. In the neutral transition metal chelate, Cu(acac)₂en, the bands at 432, 453 and 542 cm^{-1} are assigned to M–N str. and M–O str. respectively while in Ni(acac)₂en, the M–N str. vibration arises at 465 cm^{-1} whereas M–O str. vibration occurs at 543 cm^{-1} (Table 2).

UV-Visible spectra :

The electronic absorption bands (Table 3) for the chelate metal complex ligand *N,N'*-ethylenebis(acetylacetonato)copper(II) and *N,N'*-ethylenebis(acetylacetonato)nickel(II) recorded in the wavelength range 233–334 nm indicates $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in aromatic ring and C=N chromophore. On complexation with rubidium and caesium salts, the spectra of all Cu^{II} or Ni^{II} bridge complexes exhibit three to four bands in the wavelength range, 226–406 nm. This suggests that there is no changes in stereochemistry of complexes after adduct formation. This is also supported by the magnetic value of the adducts. The absorption bands of medium shoulder in Cu(acac)₂en and Ni(acac)₂en at 332 and 334 nm respectively indicates square planar geometry of Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ with coordination number 4. For the binuclear complexes of Cu(acac)₂en or Ni(acac)₂en with rubidium or caesium metal salts of organic acids, similar type of electronic spectral bands are observed. This suggests similar square planar

Structure I

Structure II

Structure III

Fig. 1

geometry of $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}$ in all its binuclear adducts with no change in coordination number. Neither Cu^{2+} nor Ni^{2+} gets attached with rubidium or

caesium metal salts of organic acids on complexation. Absence of absorption bands in the wavelength region 700–1200 nm in the binuclear complexes further confirms that the coordination number of Cu^{2+} or Ni^{2+} in the binuclear adducts have not been raised but it remains 4 with square planar geometry. In the binuclear adducts of $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}$, the spin of the Cu^{II} ions are so strongly coupled that they show diamagnetic behaviour¹⁴. The diamagnetic nature of the binuclear adducts of NiES suggest for their square planar geometry with coordination number 4.

The bonding between N,N' -ethylenebis(acetylacetonato) metal(II) complex $[\text{M}_a(\text{acac})_2\text{en}]$ and the alkali metal is most likely to occur by dative bonding via two enolic oxygen atoms of the ligand which has been supported by the IR spectra, magnetic properties and electronic spectral studies of the adducts¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The physico-chemical studies as discussed above suggests square planar geometry of $[\text{M}_a(\text{acac})_2\text{en}]$ (where $\text{M}_a = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ or Ni^{II}) with coordination number 4 in all its alkali metal adducts. The probable structure and bonding of the binuclear complexes having general formula $[\text{Ma}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}.\text{M}_b\text{L}]$ may be shown as in Fig. 2.

Antimicrobial activity :

The *in vitro* antimicrobial screening to the synthesized hetero binuclear complexes were carried out against the bacteria *Escherichia coli* MTCC 739, *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC 96 and fungi *Candida albicans* MTCC 227. The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) val-

Table 2. Selected infrared spectral data of metal chelate and their hetero binuclear complexes

Compd.	~ 1600 cm^{-1}	~ 1500 cm^{-1}	~ 1100 cm^{-1}	~ 400/500 cm^{-1}
$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}$	1595	1515	1120	432, 453, 542
$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}.\text{CsTNP}$	1602	1516	1110	420, 409, 525, 544
$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}.\text{RbTNP}$	1604	1504	1108	410, 432, 534
$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}.\text{Rb8HQ}$	1598	1497	1112	415, 486, 580
$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}.\text{Cs8HQ}$	1598	1497	1112	420, 467, 590
$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}.\text{RbDNP}$	1603	1513	1105	420, 460, 580, 506, 528
$\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}.\text{CsDNP}$	1579	1516	1102	408, 415, 540, 580, 453
$\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}$	1585	1510	1122	465, 543
$\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}.\text{CsTNP}$	1610	1517	1115	410, 490, 560, 525
$\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}.\text{RbTNP}$	1608	1512	1113	460, 508, 520, 545
$\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}.\text{Rb8HQ}$	1604	1509	1108	408, 494, 520, 560
$\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2\text{en}.\text{Rb1N2N}$	1603	1518	1110	420, 460, 492, 526, 550

Table 3. Absorption spectra of metal chelate and their hetero binuclear complexes

Compd.	Absorption spectra (nm)
Cu(acac) ₂ en	260, 281, 332
Cu(acac) ₂ en.CsTNP	238, 293, 382
Cu(acac) ₂ en.RbTNP	231, 348, 376
Cu(acac) ₂ en.Rb8HQ	255, 310, 384
Cu(acac) ₂ en.Cs8HQ	248, 308, 384
Cu(acac) ₂ en.RbDNP	387, 394, 406
Cu(acac) ₂ en.CsDNP	226, 356, 368
Ni(acac) ₂ en	233, 260, 267, 334
Ni(acac) ₂ en.CsTNP	240, 341, 387
Ni(acac) ₂ en.RbTNP	240, 298, 348, 389
Ni(acac) ₂ en.Rb8HQ	240, 348, 392
Ni(acac) ₂ en.RbIn2N	238, 294, 384

Fig. 2. Suggested structure for the hetero binuclear complexes, where $M_a = \text{Cu}$ or Ni , $M_b = \text{Rb}$ or Cs .

ues of the investigated complexes are given in Table 4. The antimicrobial activity of the complexes can be considered on the basis of chelation theory. Chelation causes overlap of the ligand orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge of the metal ion with the donor groups. This reduces the polarizability of the metal which enhances the lipophilicity of the complexes causing breakdown of permeability of the cells. This results in interference of the normal cell process of the micro organisms which restricts further growth of the micro organisms¹⁸.

Experimental

A.R. grade reagents have been used for synthesizing all the complexes. IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrophotometer, Shimadzu model 8201PC in KBr phase. Electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 15 UVB VIS spectrophotometer. Melting point

Table 4. Antimicrobial activities (MIC values) of the investigated hetero binuclear complexes

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i> MTCC 739	<i>S. aureus</i> MTCC 96	<i>C. albicans</i> MTCC 227
Cu(acac) ₂ en.RbDNP	100	50	100
Cu(acac) ₂ en.CsDNP	100	100	100
Cu(acac) ₂ en.CsTNP	>200	>200	100
Ni(acac) ₂ en.RbTNP	200	200	100
Ni(acac) ₂ en.CsDNP	100	100	50
Ni(acac) ₂ en.Rb8HQ	50	100	100
Streptomycin	100	25	-
Fluconazole	-	-	100

of the compounds was determined on electrical tempo T-1150 melting point apparatus. Molar conductivities were measured with the help of Systronic digital direct conductivity meter-306. Magnetic measurements were carried on Faraday Magnetic Susceptibility balance. Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} ions have been estimated by complexometric EDTA titrations; estimation of Rb and Cs were done by standard methods.

Synthetic procedures :

The Schiff base of *N,N'*-ethylenebis(acetylacetonate) was prepared by refluxing the acetylacetonate and ethylenediamine in 2 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol for 5 min. The pale yellow coloured Schiff base obtained was filtered off, washed with ice cold ethanol and dried. A solution of copper(II) acetate hydrate (2.0 g) or nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate (2.5 g) in ethanol (15 ml) was added slowly with constant stirring to a hot solution of the Schiff base (2.24 g). The mixture was further refluxed with constant stirring with the help of magnetic stirrer at 80 °C for 1 h. The solution upon cooling deposited brown coloured copper complex or the pale brown coloured nickel complex. These were filtered off, washed thoroughly with ethanol and dried in electric oven at 80 °C.

Hetero binuclear complexes constituting Cu^{II} metal ion and rubidium or caesium metal :

N,N'-Ethylenebis(acetylacetonate) copper(II) [Cu(acac)₂en] was taken in absolute alcohol in a conical flask and rubidium or caesium metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol or 8-hydroxyquinoline were added to it in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 80 °C with constant stirring for 1 h. The characteristic

coloured adducts were precipitated in hot condition which was filtered, washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol and dried in electric oven at 80 °C.

Hetero binuclear complexes constituting Ni^{II} metal ion and rubidium or caesium metal :

N,N'-Ethylenebis(acetylacetonato)nickel(II) [Ni(acac)₂en] was taken in absolute alcohol in a conical flask and rubidium or caesium metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol or 8-hydroxyquinoline were added to it in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 80 °C with constant stirring for 1 h. The characteristic coloured adducts were precipitated in hot condition which was filtered, washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol and dried in electric oven at 80 °C.

Antimicrobial activity :

The hetero binuclear complexes have been tested for *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity against the bacteria *Escherichia coli* MTCC 739, *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC 96 and fungi *Candida albicans* MTCC 227 by microplate method of Eloff¹⁸, using broth nutrient as the medium. Different dilution of chemicals were prepared in DMSO and added to the well. The microplates were incubated at 37 (± 1 °C) and examined after 12 h and reabsorbed after 48 h. After 48 h, each was screened and lowest dilution of the chemical without any growth of the micro organism was recorded as MIC. These test micro organisms were also checked with some antibiotics like streptomycin and antifungal like fluconazole.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Director, CDRI, Lucknow and Head, Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi for conducting spectral measurements and magnetic measurements.

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